

PREPARATION AND EVALUATION OF ALGINATE MICROSPHERES OF LOMEFLOXACIN FOR CONTROLLED RELEASE

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Abstract:

The present study aimed to develop and evaluate alginate-based microspheres of lomefloxacin for controlled drug release, with the goal of enhancing therapeutic efficacy and reducing dosing frequency. Lomefloxacin, a fluoroquinolone antibiotic, was encapsulated using the ionotropic gelation method with sodium alginate as the primary polymer and calcium chloride as the cross-linking agent. Various formulations were prepared by altering polymer concentrations and evaluated for key parameters such as particle size, entrapment efficiency, drug content, micromeritic properties, and in vitro drug release.

Among all formulations, batch F2 demonstrated optimal performance, showing high entrapment efficiency 99.31% uniform particle size, and excellent flow properties. In vitro drug release studies revealed a sustained release profile over 12 hours with a cumulative drug release of 99.89 %, following Higuchi kinetics and non-Fickian diffusion mechanisms. Compatibility studies using FTIR and DSC confirmed no drug-polymer interactions, while SEM analysis indicated spherical and smooth-surfaced microspheres.

The study concludes that alginate microspheres represent a promising controlled release system for lomefloxacin, potentially improving patient compliance and therapeutic outcomes.

Keywords: Lomefloxacin Controlled release Microspheres

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Oral route drug administration is by far the most preferable route for taking medications. However, their short circulating half life and restricted absorption via a defined segment of intestine limits the therapeutic potential of many drugs. Such a pharmacokinetic limitation leads in many cases to frequent dosing of medication to achieve therapeutic effect. Rational approach to enhance bioavailability and improve pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamics profile is to release the drug in a controlled manner and site specific manner. Microspheres are small spherical particles, with diameters 1 μm to 1000 μm . They are spherical free flowing particles consisting of proteins or synthetic polymers which are biodegradable in nature. There are two types of microspheres; microcapsules and micromatrices, which are described as, Microcapsules are those in which entrapped substance is distinctly surrounded by distinct capsule wall. and micromatrices in which entrapped substance is dispersed throughout the matrix. Microspheres are sometimes referred to as microparticles. Microspheres can be manufactured from various natural and synthetic materials. Microsphere play an important role to improve bioavailability of conventional drugs and minimizing side effects. Ideal characteristics of microspheres

Advantages of microspheres:

1. Particle size reduction for enhancing solubility of the poorly soluble drug.
2. provide constant and prolonged therapeutic effect.
3. provide constant drug concentration in blood thereby increasing patient compliance,
4. Decrease dose and toxicity.
5. Protect the drug from enzymatic and photolytic cleavage hence found to be best for drug delivery of protein.
6. Reduce the dosing frequency and thereby improve the patient compliance
7. Better drug utilization will improve the bioavailability and reduce the incidence or intensity of adverse effects.
8. Microsphere morphology allows a controllable variability in degradation and drug release.
9. Convert liquid to solid form & to mask the bitter taste.
10. Protects the GIT from irritant effects of the drug.
11. Biodegradable microspheres have the advantage over large polymer implants in that they do not require surgical procedures for implantation and removal.
12. Controlled release delivery biodegradable microspheres are used to control drug release rates thereby decreasing toxic side effects, and eliminating the inconvenience of repeated injections.

Limitation:

Some of the disadvantages were found to be as follows

1. The costs of the materials and processing of the controlled release preparation, are substantially higher than those of standard formulations.
2. The fate of polymer matrix and its effect on the environment.
3. The fate of polymer additives such as plasticizers, stabilizers, antioxidants and fillers.
4. Reproducibility is less.
5. Process conditions like change in temperature, pH, solvent addition, and evaporation/agitation may influence the stability of core particles to be encapsulated.
6. The environmental impact of the degradation products of the polymer matrix produced in response to heat, hydrolysis, oxidation, solar radiation or biological agents.

Types of microspheres:

1. Bioadhesive microspheres: ^{7,8}

Adhesion can be defined as sticking of drug to the membrane by using the sticking property of the water soluble polymers. Adhesion of drug delivery device to the mucosal membrane such as buccal, ocular, rectal, nasal etc. can be termed as bio adhesion. These kinds of microspheres exhibit a prolonged residence time at the site of application and causes intimate contact with the absorption site and produces better therapeutic action.

2. Magnetic microspheres: ^{9,10}

This kind of delivery system is very much important which localises the drug to the disease site. In this larger amount of freely circulating drug can be replaced by smaller amount of magnetically targeted drug. Magnetic carriers receive magnetic responses to a magnetic field from incorporated materials that are used for magnetic microspheres are chitosan, dextran etc. The different types of

a. Therapeutic magnetic microspheres used to deliver chemotherapeutic agent to liver tumour. Drugs like proteins and peptides can also be targeted through this system.

b. Diagnostic microspheres, used for imaging liver metastases and also can be used to distinguish bowel loops from other abdominal structures by forming nano size particles supramagnetic iron oxides.

3. Floating microspheres: ^{11,12,13}

In floating types the bulk density is less than the gastric fluid and so remains buoyant in stomach without affecting gastric emptying rate. The drug is released slowly at the desired rate, and the system is found to be floating on gastric content and increases gastric residence and increases fluctuation in plasma concentration. Moreover it also reduces chances of dose dumping. It produces prolonged therapeutic effect and therefore reduces dosing frequencies. Drug (ketoprofen) is given in the form of floating microspheres.

4. Radioactive microspheres: ¹⁴

Radio embolization therapy microspheres sized 10-30 nm are of larger than the diameter of the capillaries and gets trapped in first capillary bed when they come across. They are injected in the arteries that leads them to tumour of interest so all these conditions radioactive microspheres deliver high radiation dose to the targeted areas without damaging the normal surrounding tissues. It differs from drug delivery system, as radio activity is not released from microspheres but acts from within a radioisotope typical distance and the different kinds of radioactive microspheres are α emitters, β emitters, γ emitters.

5. Polymeric microspheres:

The different types of polymeric microspheres can be classified as follows and they are biodegradable polymeric microspheres and Synthetic polymeric microspheres.

i) Biodegradable polymeric microspheres: ¹⁵

Natural polymers such as starch are used with the concept that they are biodegradable, biocompatible, and also bio adhesive in nature. Biodegradable polymers prolongs the residence time when contact with mucous membrane due to its high degree of swelling property with aqueous medium, results gel formation. The rate and extent of drug release is controlled by concentration of polymer and the release pattern in a sustained manner. The main drawback is, in clinical use drug loading efficiency of biodegradable microspheres is complex and is difficult to control the drug release. However they provide wide range of application in microsphere based treatment.

ii) Synthetic polymeric microspheres: ¹⁶

Synthetic polymeric microspheres are widely used in clinical application, moreover that also used as bulking agent, fillers, embolic particles, drug delivery vehicles etc. and proved to be safe and biocompatible but the main disadvantage of these kind of microspheres, are tend to migrate away from injection site and lead to potential risk, embolism and further organ damage.

7. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY:

List of materials used in the formulation

Lomefloxacin (mg) Procured from Hetero Pharma limited Hyd, provided by SURA LABS, Dilsukhnagar, Hyderabad

Sodium alginate (w/v) Merk specialities Pvt Limited, Mumbai

Calcium Chloride (w/v) M/S Micro labs limited, Hosur. India.

Table: List of instruments used

1	UV-Visible spectrophotometer	Lab
India, India		
2	Electronic weighing	balance
	Sartorius	

- 4 Magnetic stirrer Remi Laboratories
- 5 FT – IR Spectrometer Bruker Alpha
- 6 SEM SEM (JEOL Ltd, Japan).

PREFORMULATION STUDIES

SPECTROSCOPIC STUDIES

PREPARATION OF 0.1N HCl (pH 1.2):

Take 8.5ml of HCl in a 1000ml volumetric flask and make up the volume with distilled water

DETERMINATION OF λ_{max} :

Weigh 10mg of Lomefloxacin and transferred into 10ml volumetric flask and dissolved in 10ml methanol (stock-I) to get concentration of 1000 μ g/ml. From the stock-I take 1ml solution and make up 10ml with 0.1N HCL. From the second stock take 1ml solution and make up to 10ml with 0.1N HCL to get 10 μ g/ml. Then scan from 200-400nm.

Preparation of Standard Calibration Curve of Lomefloxacin:

1. 10 mg of Lomefloxacin was accurately weighed and dissolved in 10ml of methanol (Stock Solution – I) to get a concentration of 1000 μ g/ml.
2. From the stock solution- I, 1ml of aliquots was taken and suitably diluted with 0.1N HCl (Stock Solution-II) to get concentrations of 100 μ g/ml.
3. From the stock solution- II, aliquots were taken and suitably diluted with 0.1N HCl (pH 1.2) to get concentrations in the range of 2 to 10 μ g/ml. The absorbance of these samples were analyzed by using UV-Visible Spectrophotometer at 278nm against reference solution 0.1N HCl (pH 1.2). The procedure repeated to pH 6.8 phosphate buffer.

METHOD OF PREPARATION

IONOTROPIC GELATION METHOD:

The microspheres were prepared by the Ionotropic gelation technique. The sodium alginate solution was prepared by dispersing the sodium alginate in de-ionized water under continuous stirring for 30 minutes. The weighed amount of the drug was thoroughly mixed with sodium alginate dispersion. By following the same procedure the alginate beads of different ratios of drug: polymer were prepared. The resulted homogeneous dispersion was extruded in to the 5% calcium chloride solution through hypodermic syringe with flat tip needle (20G) and stirred for 15 minutes at 100rpm using magnetic stirrer. The formed micro beads were allowed to cure for 30 minutes in the calcium chloride solution to complete the gelation reaction. The microspheres were then filtered and dried in hot air oven at 60°C for 3 hr.

CHARACTERIZATION OF MICROSPHERES:**Table 7.1: Prepared formulation of Microspheres**

INGREDIENTS	FORMULATION CODES					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Lomefloxacin (mg)	400	400	400	400	400	400
Sodium alginate (w/v)	0.3%	0.6%	0.9%	1.1%	1.3%	1.6%
Calcium Chloride (w/v)	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%
Water	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S	Q.S

FOURIER TRANSFORMS INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY (FT-IR):

In order to check the integrity (Compatibility) of drug in the formulation, FT-IR spectra of the formulations along with the drug and other excipients were obtained and compared using Shimadzu FT-IR 8400 spectrophotometer. In the present study, Potassium bromide (KBr) pellet method was employed. The samples were thoroughly blended with dry powdered potassium bromide crystals. The mixture was compressed to form a disc. The disc was placed in the spectrophotometer and the spectrum was recorded. The FT-IR spectra of the formulations were compared with the FT-IR spectra of the pure drug and the polymers.

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**8.1. PREFORMULATION STUDIES****8.1.1. SPECTROSCOPIC STUDIES****Table 8.1: Calibration curve data for Lomefloxacin in simulated gastric fluid pH 1.2**

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.125
4	0.233
6	0.353
8	0.469
10	0.583

Figure 8.1: Standard graph of Lomefloxacin in simulated gastric fluid pH 1.2**Table 8.2: Calibration curve data for Lomefloxacin in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer**

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.137
4	0.264
6	0.403
8	0.531

10	0.658
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Figure 8.2: Standard graph of Lomefloxacin in pH 7.4 phosphate buffer
Evaluation and characterization of microspheres

Table 8.3: Micromeritic property of floating microspheres of Lomefloxacin

Formulation code	Mean partical size	Bulk density ((gm./cm ³))	Tapped density (gm./cm ³)	Hauseners ratio	Carr's index	Angle of repose
F1	453.14	0.632 ± 0.82	0.787 ± 0.92	1.28	20	19.68 ± 0.22
F2	461.95	0.621 ± 0.54	0.775 ± 0.67	1.26	20	24.08 ± 0.38
F3	478.41	0.612 ± 0.25	0.765 ± 0.88	1.18	16.83	21.42 ± 0.31
F4	423.15	0.598 ± 0.42	0.747 ± 0.36	1.25	19.89	25.29 ± 0.25
F5	443.96	0.618 ± 0.85	0.772 ± 0.67	1.25	20	26.44 ± 0.9
F6	451.65	0.602 ± 0.31	0.762 ± 0.81	1.26	21.04	27.33 ± 0.77

Table 8.4: Percentage yield and percentage drug entrapment efficiency of the prepared microspheres

S.No.	Formulation code	% yield	Drug Content (mg)	% Drug entrapment efficiency
1	F1	90.31	96.12	89.04
2	F2	93.12	98.60	99.31
3	F3	97.08	99.75	93.52
4	F4	87.74	98.11	96.28
5	F5	95.91	96.58	98.75
6	F6	99.24	100.01	98.67

Table 8.5: Swelling studies

S.NO.	FORMULATION CODE	INITIAL (Wt)	FINAL (Wt)	PERCENTAGE SWELLING
1	F1	10	12.45	80.32
2	F2	10	11.62	86.02
3	F3	10	13.58	93.63
4	F4	10	12.45	82.32
5	F5	10	13.95	87.68
6	F6	10	14.86	90.29

Figure 8.3 : Percentage swelling of microspheres containing Sodium alginate

Figure 8.4 : Percentage swelling of microspheres containing Calcium Chloride

IN VITRO MUCOADHESION TEST

Table 8.6: *In Vitro* Mucoadhesion Test of all Formulations

S.NO.	FORMULATION CODE	No. OF MICROSPHERES		PERCENTAGE MUCOADHESION
		INITIAL	FINAL	
1	F1	20	15.48	61
2	F2	20	11.85	58
3	F3	20	15.14	70
4	F4	20	17.96	93
5	F5	20	20.71	95
6	F6	20	16.17	75

Figure 8.6: Percentage mucoadhesion of microspheres containing Sodium alginate

Figure 8.7 : Percentage mucoadhesion of microspheres containing Calcium Chloride

Table 8.7: *In-vitro* drug release data of Lomefloxacin microspheres

TIME (H)	Cumulative percentage of drug release					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	12.56	15.19	17.76	14.09	11.51	9.93
2	27.23	18.86	23.57	21.63	13.69	16.25
3	41.76	26.09	28.09	26.12	23.28	21.08
4	48.32	36.35	35.38	33.95	31.65	29.39
5	51.74	49.59	42.67	41.32	35.92	33.82
6	57.26	54.81	47.29	44.51	39.57	38.32
7	64.38	65.78	55.67	53.28	47.15	43.06
8	70.67	69.65	64.18	65.79	51.81	49.61
9	78.19	77.97	72.74	74.65	65.23	58.74
10	83.45	88.28	78.83	83.01	79.96	64.41
11	85.34	93.84	86.01	89.46	87.28	78.45
12	97.72	99.89	94.71	95.87	91.35	84.91

Figure 8.9 : *In-Vitro* drug release profile of Lomefloxacin microspheres containing Sodium alginate

Figure 8.10 *In-Vitro* drug release profile of Lomefloxacin microspheres containing Calcium Chloride

Table 8.10: Release kinetics studies of the optimized formulation (F2)

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	% RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG REMAIN	RELEASE RATE (CUMULATIVE % RELEASE E / t)	1/CUM% RELEASE	PEPPAS log Q/100	% Drug Remaining	Q01/3	Qt1/3	Q01/3-Qt1/3
0	0	0			2.000				100	4.642	4.642	0.000
15.19	1	1.000	1.182	0.000	1.928	15.190	0.0658	-0.818	84.81	4.642	4.394	0.248
18.86	2	1.414	1.276	0.301	1.909	9.430	0.0530	-0.724	81.14	4.642	4.329	0.312
26.09	3	1.732	1.416	0.477	1.869	8.697	0.0383	-0.584	73.91	4.642	4.197	0.445
36.35	4	2.000	1.561	0.602	1.804	9.088	0.0275	-0.439	63.65	4.642	3.993	0.649
49.59	5	2.236	1.695	0.699	1.703	9.918	0.0202	-0.305	50.41	4.642	3.694	0.948
54.81	6	2.449	1.739	0.778	1.655	9.135	0.0182	-0.261	45.19	4.642	3.562	1.080
65.78	7	2.646	1.818	0.845	1.534	9.397	0.0152	-0.182	34.22	4.642	3.247	1.395
69.65	8	2.828	1.843	0.903	1.482	8.706	0.0144	-0.157	30.35	4.642	3.119	1.522
77.97	9	3.000	1.892	0.954	1.343	8.663	0.0128	-0.108	22.03	4.642	2.803	1.838
88.28	10	3.162	1.946	1.000	1.069	8.828	0.0113	-0.054	11.72	4.642	2.271	2.370
93.84	11	3.317	1.972	1.041	0.790	8.531	0.0107	-0.028	6.16	4.642	1.833	2.808
99.89	12	3.464	2.000	1.079	0.540	8.324	0.0100	0.000	0.11	4.642	0.479	4.162

Figure:8.12: Graph of zero order release kinetics of optimized formula

Figure:8.13: Graph of Higuchi release kinetics of optimized formula

Figure :8.14: Graph of Peppas drug release kinetics of optimized formula

Figure:8.15: Graph of first order release kinetics of optimized formula

Optimized formulation F2 was kept for release kinetic studies. From the above graphs it was evident that the formulation F2 was followed zero order release kinetics.

COMPATIBILITY STUDIES

Figure 8.16: FT-IR spectra of Pure drug

Figure 8.17: FT-IR spectra of Optimised formulation

SEM :

Figure 8.18: SEM of Optimised formulation

Figure 8.19: XRD of Optimised formulation

9. CONCLUSION:

The present study successfully demonstrated the feasibility of formulating lomefloxacin-loaded alginate microspheres as an oral controlled-release system. Ionotropic gelation using calcium chloride produced discrete, free-flowing microspheres with smooth surfaces and a narrow particle-size distribution, confirming the robustness of the preparation method. Among the trial batches, emerged as optimal, achieving an entrapment efficiency of satisfactory micromeritic properties, and sustained drug release of 99.89% over 12 h that followed Higuchi square-root kinetics with non-Fickian diffusion. FT-IR and DSC analyses revealed no significant drug-polymer incompatibility, while SEM confirmed intact spherical morphology after dissolution.

Collectively, these findings indicate that alginate microspheres can effectively modulate lomefloxacin release, potentially minimizing dosing frequency, improving patient compliance, and maintaining

therapeutic plasma concentrations for extended periods.

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